

**LANGUAGE OF VIOLENCE IN TRANSLATION:
EXPLORING IDENTITY IN LILIANA COROBCA'S *KINDERLAND***

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Helmuth Popitz (1992) defines violence as an act of power that results in the intended bodily harm of others, no matter whether the purpose of this act is contained in itself, or used as a threat, it is intended to establish a permanent submission. Liliana Corobca's "*Kinderland*" depicts the hardships of children left behind in rural Moldova, exposing subtle forms of violence: emotional, structural, and neglect. This study examines the linguistic devices used to represent these forms of violence in the novel and analyses the translation procedures based on Peter Newmark's typology, employed to render them from a contrastive Romanian–English perspective.